

More on the crab spider *Thomisus stenningi* Pocock, 1900 in South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The female of *Thomisus stenningi* Pocock, 1900 was described from King William's Town in the Eastern Cape and the male by Lessert in 1923. *Thomisus stenningi* has since then been recorded from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known in all the provinces. Their general morphology is discussed, along with notes on their lifestyle, conservation, and distribution in South Africa.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Thomisus* Walckenaer, 1805 is a large genus known from 142 species (World Spider Catalog, 2025). During surveys of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of *Thomisus* specimens have been collected. Sixteen species are presently recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

The Southern African *Thomisus* species were revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). Numerous specimens were identified as *T. stenningi* Pocock, 1900, a species that was described from a female from King William's Town in the Eastern Cape. Males collected with these females correspond to the description of the species *T. weberi* by Lessert (1923) from the Amatola Mountains, Hogsback, in the Eastern Cape. This resulted in the recognition of *T. weberi* as the male and a junior synonym of *T. stenningi*.

Before the revision by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983), the species was known only from South Africa, Angola, and Kenya (Caporiacco, 1949). Many specimens were examined during the revision, and the species' distribution was extended to include Botswana, Equatorial Guinea, Lesotho, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species was also later recorded from Malawi (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988) and Yemen (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Harten, 2007).

In this paper, the general morphology is discussed with notes on their lifestyle, conservation and distribution in South Africa.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens collected during the SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. The SANSA project solicited photographs the SANSA Virtual Museum, and some of the pictures in this article were received from the public.

TAXONOMY

Thomisus stenningi Pocock, 1900

Thomisus stenningi Pocock, 1900: 332 (f); Comellini, 1957: 29 (f); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 28 (mf, S of *Thomisus weberi*); 1988: 435 (mf); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Harten, 2007: 180; Saaristo, 2010: 285; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020a: 60; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kelly, 2024: 11.

Thomisus weberi Lessert, 1923: 174 (m); Caporiacco, 1949: 456.

Descriptive characters: Female can change colour and are either yellow or white (Figs 1–2), only occasionally with pink patches. Carapace with eye region suffused with white; integument with numerous short setae. Abdomen same colour as carapace; wider than long; tubercles sometimes with dark spots (Fig. 11). Legs without markings, same colour as carapace. Epigyne composed of two half-circles (Fig. 7); spermathecae as shown in Fig. 8.

Figures 1–3. *Thomisus stenningi*. 1. Yellow female from Mpetsane in the Free State. 2. White female from Heidelberg in Gauteng. 3. Male from Free State. Credits: 1. Allen Jones. 2. Johan van Zyl. 3. Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Thomisus stenningi*. 4–6. Male palp. 7. Epigyne. 8. Spermathecae. Credits: 4–5. Ruan Booysen. 6–8. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1988).

Males vary in colour. Carapace varies from pale brown eye region suffused with white (Figs 3 & 9); some pale brown with darker mediolateral bands (Figs 9–10); clothed with numerous erect setae. Abdomen cream to fawn with faint bands; clothed with numerous erect setae. Legs fawn in some with a greenish tint; patella, tibia and metatarsi I and II are slightly darker, with faint bands (Figs 9–10). Palp embolus slender (Figs 4–6); retrolateral tibial apophysis long, reaching the upper edge of the cymbium; patella bears an apophysis on the retrolateral side (Figs 4–6).

LIFESTYLE

Free-living plant dwellers that have frequently been collected from flowers. Females can change their colour from white to yellow, and occasionally, freshly caught specimens have a faint pink tint (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983). Adults were collected throughout the year, including winter. Their numbers were the highest from October to March.

The species has also been frequently sampled from crops: cotton, potatoes, lucerne, pecans, pine plantations, pistachio orchards, strawberries and wheat (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 12. *Thomisus stenningi* female from Kogelberg changing from white to yellow. Credits: Felix Riegel.

Figures 9–11. *Thomisus stenningi*. 9. Male from Heidelberg in Gauteng. 10. Male anterior view. 11. White female from the Eastern Cape. Credits: 9. Johan van Zyl. 10. Wolf Avni. 11. Martie Rheeder.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species is well protected in several reserves and parks in South Africa. In the Eastern Cape it was listed from the Amathole Mountains (Haddad *et al.*, 2023), the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020b) and the Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz 2023). In the Free State it is listed from the Golden Gate National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024) and the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013) and in Gauteng from the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2024) and the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023).

In the Limpopo sampled from the Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001), Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009) and the Western Cape from the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021), Kirstenbosch National Botanical Gardens (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) and Garden Route National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: *Thomisus stenningi* has been recorded throughout Africa, including South Africa, Botswana, Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Angola, Guinea, and Zaire. The species also occurs in the Seychelles and Yemen.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 13): In South Africa, the species has been extensively documented across all nine provinces, ranging from 6 to 3,337 meters above sea level. It has been recorded from all the floral biomes in South Africa.

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